

DIGITAL LEARNING KIT IN BREAD AND PASTRY PRODUCTION AND THE PERFORMANCE OF THE CORE SKILLS AMONG THE GRADE 9 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

These trying times that Covid-19 has become a global crisis led the Department of Education in giving special attention to the online platform in the delivery of educational information and services to students. This study aimed to determine the impact of the digital learning kit in Bread and Pastry Production on the performance of the core skills among the Grade 9 students. Descriptive method of research was used in the study. The respondents were sixty (60) students selected by means of purposive sampling. Based on the results, the respondents perceived the digital learning kit to be acceptable in terms of objectives, content, instructional design, presentation, and layout and usefulness having an overall mean of 4.41, 4.51, 4.39, 4.52, and 4.50 correspondingly. Furthermore, in terms of the performance of the respondents of the core skills as to cognitive skills, 91.7% got an excellent rating; 6.7% very good; and 1.7% good rating. In terms of technical skills performance, 48% got an excellent rating and 52% very good. Finally, the results show that the digital learning kit in terms of objectives, content, instructional design, presentation and layout, and usefulness when correlated with cognitive skills performance shows the results of .346**, .455**, .469**, .543** and .455**. As to technical skills, .422**, .320*, .332**, .452** and .420** respectively. Considering the results, the digital learning kit is an effective instructional material that can be used in teaching Bread and Pastry Production. Based on the findings of this study, the hypothesis stating that there is a no significant relationship between the digital learning kit in Bread and Pastry Production and the core skills performances in terms of cognitive and technical skills of the respondents in Bread and Pastry Production, is therefore REJECTED.

Keywords: Digital Learning Kit, Objectives, Contents, Student performance, Cognitive Skills. Technical Skill